

COUNSELLING STRATEGIES FOR PARENTING ADOLESCENTS TOWARDS SMOOTH TRANSITION TO ADULthood

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Abstract

Parenting is not an easy task everywhere in the world particularly parenting of adolescents. It is indeed an Herculean task because of the sensitivity of that stage of development which requires mutual understanding between the parents and adolescents. This paper focused on adolescents and their problems, parenting adolescents and its challenges. Also, counselling strategies that could be employed by parents for smooth transition of adolescents to adulthood were discussed. It is recommended that basically, parents require wisdom, knowledge and understanding to be able to successfully raise adolescent towards adulthood.

Keywords: *Counseling, Parenting, Adolescents and Adulthood.*

Introduction

Adulthood is a period of upheaval not only for the youth but also for parents. It is a stage of life expected to be passed through by every growing teenager before the attainment of adulthood. It is a complex stage of development which the child passes through and obviously a concern for the parents who would not want their children to go astray outside the accepted norms of the society. Weill (2005) describes adolescent's experience as "walking a tightrope without a net". He further asserts that it is a tumultuous period of life which is full of fraught, feeling of awkwardness, anxiety and confusion. Accordingly to him, an adolescent is caught between childhood

and adulthood. It is a flexible stage whereby the child can easily be influenced or manipulated either positively or negatively.

Since human beings differ in their developmental traits, it is pertinent to understand this period. Ademuyiwa (2003) stated that people differ from each other physically, mentally, socially and emotionally and therefore, special attention must be paid to realize their full potentials. This period should further be seen and addressed as a period for mutual rapport and interaction for healthful development rather than battle on the part of parents.

Idowu (2003) quoting Watson (1996) observed that human beings put more emphasis on the ability to give birth to children rather than the ability to rear and nurture them. He advised further that children should be brought forth only when they can be catered for. The role of counselling strategies in nurturing and mentoring children through their developmental stages cannot be overemphasized. Clausen (1996) posited that counselling assists parents in achieving Positive Parenting Project (PPP), he advised further that parents of adolescents need to continuously nurture their parenting skills and they need to develop their self esteem, self concept and invest in their skills as parents. Hence, parents should seek professional assistance of the guidance counsellor at all times in order to be well equipped with counselling strategies for parenting the adolescents into responsible and respected adults in the society.

What is adolescence?

According to Moronkola (2003), the word adolescence was coined from the Latin word that means "grown into maturity". The classification of adolescence started in the 19th century when the economic pressure and the burden of the adolescent on the parents took a more challenging dimension which warranted the classification of children into jobs outside their parents'

homes. The World Book (2000) called it the "invention" of adolescence and explained that it started with the change in the pattern of work during the industrial revolution in the 1800 whereby ages 12-16 started new work outside the family to prepare for adulthood thereby taking jobs in mines, factories, mills, craft apprentices, attending school etc.

Adolescence in African society was not actually defined with prime linkage to job classification but with the general developmental traits such as helping the parents in the farm, assisting them domestically, attaining puberty and preparation for marriage and so on. Age group classifications with social and traditional accomplices were more pronounced (Olubayo Fatiregun, 2003). Therefore, until the embrace of the western culture, adolescence varied at different levels of recognition from society to society. Other schools of thought elaborate more on adolescence. For example, Collier (1997) described adolescence as a phase in the human life-span between childhood and adulthood with special significance. He stated further that it is an experimental bridge between childhood and adulthood in which the adolescent tries to establish his personal identity, and to search answers to the questions of who one is, who one wants to be, and what worth one is.

On the other hand, adolescence is seen by Crystal (1994) as that period of personal development marked by the on set of puberty and continuing through the early teenage years and associated with the process of physical maturation occurring more quickly in girls than boys. Moronkola and Okanlawon (2003) quoted Roger (1985), Bryne and Benneth (1979) that adolescence is a process rather than a time period of achieving the attitude and beliefs needed for effective childhood and adulthood wherein a person prepares for becoming a worker, a parent and citizen. It is likened to a tunnel, very long and much darkened in some people than others but through which all must pass. In essence, adolescence is that period in which the child gradually transits to maturity and adulthood both in roles, growth and

through which all must pass. In essence, adolescence is that period in which the child gradually transits to maturity and adulthood both in roles, growth and development.

There is no exact universal or biological age for all the adolescents. This is so because the classification of adolescents varies to a certain extent from one society to another. Corroborating this assertion, Crystal (1994) reported that the age range and behavioural patterns of the adolescents vary considerably from society to society. He cited examples that in the third world, working in the field and taking adult responsibilities could start as early as ages nine or ten while in the developed nations, it could take the whole of the high school period. Similarly from biological view, puberty is never attained by every growing child at a permanent set age. This maybe dictated by such important factors as nutrition and sex usually with the average of two years attained earlier in the girls than boys. Nevertheless, there is age range, which experts have put forward through observations and experiments. World Health Organisation (1993) puts it between 10 and 19 years.

Concepts of Parents and Parenting

Parents simply mean one's father and mother. However, in the African traditional context, it goes beyond the father or mother but includes all the members of the nuclear family, the extended family, neighbours and every other persons who in one way or the other are involved in the upbringing of the child. However, the heaviest burden is borne by the biological parents (father and mother). Similarly, parents also receive immediate and highest credit for successful children and sometimes, they may be blamed for their failure. Parenting or (child rearing) is the act of parenthood. It is the process of upbringing or training of a child by parents. Majorinbanks (1996) viewed it as a process of promoting and supporting the physical, emotional, social and intellectual development of a child from infancy to adulthood. In Africa, it

extends beyond the period of marriage of the children. Parenting could be positive or negative. Any lapses in this vital life act may carry serious consequence which maybe very difficult to reverse. As such children may be at risk.

Adegoke (2003) reported that adolescents at risk are those who fall into one or more of these five problematic categories such as low school achievements, drop outs, gay and lesbians, single teenage mother and runaways. These result from poor negative parenting. Positive parenting is therefore a prerequisite for adolescents towards smooth transition to adulthood.

Challenges of Parenting Adolescents

Adolescents or teenagers pose some of the most difficult challenges for parents. Awake (2004), reported that teenagers dealing with hormonal changes and an ever complex world may feel that no one can understand their feelings, especially parents. As a result, the teenager may feel angry, lonely and confused while facing complicated issues about identity, peers, sexual behaviours, drinking and drugs.

According to Twinning (2001), parents may be frustrated and angry because their teenager seems not to respond anymore to parental authority and methods of discipline that worked well in their earlier years. Also, parents may feel frustrated and helpless about the choices their teens are making and as a result, the adolescence period produces conflict in the family. Typical of parent-teen conflict according to Adegoke (2003) may include disputes over adolescents' choice of friends.

- * Spending more time with friends than with the family.
- * Peer pressure which may be (negative/positive).
- * Dispute over school and work performance
- * Over cars and driving priviledges.

- * Over/dating and sexuality.
- * Over clothing, hairstyles and make up
- * Dispute over self destructive behaviour such as smoking, drinking and use of drugs. Other problems of adolescents that are challenging for parents are
- * Poor nutrition at home which may lead to poor health.
- * Eating disorder (under/over eating).
- * Adjusting to life outside home (in school).
- * Juvenile delinquency.
- * Fluctuating moods due to uncertainty of life goals.
- * Suicide, due to failure or frustration arising from low self esteem, stress and romantic affairs.

Dealing with the issues of adolescent's can be trying for all concerned, most especially parents. They therefore require knowledge about the reasons behind the sudden changes of their adolescents; understanding, to look beyond the behaviours and perceive just what that child is going through; and wisdom, to respond in a way that continues to guide their teens towards responsible adulthood. According to Adegoke (2003), this would reduce dependence on parents while becoming increasingly responsible and independent

However, there maybe warning signs that things are not going well and that parents may need to seek outside help to arrest manifested behaviours such as, aggressive or violent behaviours, drug and alcohol abuse, promiscuity, school truancy, brushes with the law or runaway behaviours etc.

Adenigbagbe (2008) posited that in this situation, parents require counselling strategies that would assist them in interpreting the behaviours of their teenagers correctly and be able to respond to the situations in a way that will produce the best result.

Relationship Between Parents and Adolescents

During adolescence, children are beginning to form their identity and are testing and developing the interpersonal and occupational roles that they will assume as adults, therefore, it is important that cordial relationship should exist between adolescents and parents. Marcia (1980) stated that "parents must always treat them as young adults". Good and cordial relationship could promote understanding and respect for the norms being taught.

Ipaye (1983) observed that many Nigerian adolescents today see homes as contributing in various ways to the problems they face because some parents arouse ill feelings of the adolescents when the following control system is adopted:

- * Parent can be over-stern and authoritarian.
- * Being too weak and ready to yield on the part of the father, and being unable to accept responsibilities.
- * Parents not providing the proper discipline which is a part of development. The adolescent is formed by a conflict between rebellious aggressiveness and desire for submissiveness.
- * Forcing the adolescent's confidence and when he/she does tell, reacting in an emotional outburst or making a side show of it.
- * Frequently comparing the adolescent with another in the vicinity in order to point out vividly how poor he or she fares when compared with others.

Also, adolescent's view on family rules and regulations is contributory to increased disagreement between young people and parents as World Book (2000) observed that most conflict takes the form of minor arguments over day-to-day issues such as the adolescent's desire for uninterrupted privacy.

It is important for parents to build a trusting relationship with their adolescents. This can be achieved by planning and spending time for

activities together, parents keeping their promises and avoid nagging at them about their past mistakes. Parents should try to listen and talk to their adolescents no matter how busy they are. When a trusting relationship is built, they are more likely to approach parents when faced with negative peer pressure.

But if the relationship is weak, a dangerous gap may be created which can easily be exploited by other forces such as the peer group whose results may not be positive. A denied freedom at home may result in taking refuge in an unhealthy environment by the child. Relationship between parents and adolescents should portray the parents (especially the father) as a superior partner in progress with constructive corrections rather than being seen as wicked guardians and the child should be treated as a learner with peculiar traits to be carefully tendered rather than being labelled as a rebel.

Effect of Poor Parenting on Adolescents

A child well brought up will remain a source of joy and happiness for such a family in particular and the community at large. Similarly, a neglected child has a high level of probability to bring shame and disgrace to the family and a big threat to other community members near or far. Boys with poor parental backgrounds may become school dropouts who may later graduate to street boys, bus conductors or touts otherwise known as the 'area boys' found under uncompleted buildings, bridges and motor parks. Gradually they become involved in the use of hard drugs such as hard liquor and marijuana with negative physiological and social effects which further make them violent. They are less active in the day but very dangerous at night. The World Book (2000) reported that violation of the law is far more common among adolescents and young adults than in any other age group and that violent crimes and crimes against humanity is at peak. The book concluded that they are likely victims of theft, robbery, rape and adultery and that such frequent

ones typically come from disrupted or badly functioning families that also abuse drugs.

They may also become armed robbers and are easily hired by elders or dubious politicians as assassins. They are good in rioting even though they do not have any relationship with the cause. They are involved in rape and are responsible for pregnancies that result. If they are lucky to find themselves in the tertiary institutions, they may become star members of cult groups, posing threats to their fellow students and their lecturers alike. They are very aggressive during students' protests. Those who survive to adult life may become fraudster, drug barons and people of dubious characters.

Similarly, girls from such families may exhibit their male counterpart traits in less aggressive patterns. Usually they may become street hawkers, beggars and take part in commercial sex. They may give birth to unclaimed children and become early mothers of single parents. They are likely victims of female human trafficking abroad. They maybe involved in cultism and easy baits for their robber victims. They may end up becoming wives of armed robbers or ritualists of which they would also partake in future. They grow up to become society women because stable marriage is rare to achieve. Generally, both male and female adolescents of the above description see the society to be against them and therefore prepare to attack it. However, the end product of their development may bring shame to the family, threat and sleepless nights for the community members and eventually, death to themselves either by the law enforcement agents, among colleagues or self, through suicide.

Nevertheless, very small percentage could grow to become useful members of the society. To be candid, poor parenting should be abhorred by every society; the parents would be held responsible for the misfortune that befalls this group. Instances have shown where condemned armed robbers blame their parents' inabilities for their misfortune

Counselling Strategies for Parenting Adolescents towards Smooth Adulthood

Here, it is expedient to systemically advance and discuss those counselling strategies that could be employed by parents to train adolescents successfully, however our understanding of the techniques would be meaningless if what counselling entails in relation to this paper is not judiciously expatiated.

Counselling is learning-oriented process which usually occurs in an interactive relationship with the aim of helping the person more:

- (i) About the self
- (ii) About others
- (iii) About situations and events related to given issues and conditions
- (iv) Also to learn to put such understanding to being an effective member of the society, (Akinboye, 1982)

Counselling focuses upon helping the individual to cope with developmental task such as self definition, independence and the like (Adeniji, 2006), while Akinboye (1982) sees counselling as a process of helping an individual become more fully aware of himself and ways in which he is responding to the influences in the environment. From the definitions above, it can be deduced that counselling is a helping relationship which involves two or more people.

Problems faced by adolescents call for solution and parents as major stakeholders must brace up and embrace counselling strategies but hitherto, they themselves must be equipped with series of techniques by seeking assistance from professional counsellors.

The counselling strategies that could be employed by parents for effective parenting of adolescents towards smooth transition into adulthood can be itemized as following.

Observation, communication, rapport and individual counselling (Adenigbagbe, 2008). He gave its detail as follows:

- * Parents should study their adolescents through close observation.
- * Parents should note all environmental conditions that can prompt one form of behaviour or the other in their adolescents.
- * Parents should note the general behavioural characteristics of adolescents that are connected with their accelerated patterns.
- * Parents should recognize that the issue of unbearable sex drive of adolescents and their sexual affairs are handled with wisdom and patience. One must also possess full knowledge and understanding of the traits that are exhibited during this growing period i.e. physical, psychological and social development traits.
- * Parents should be consistent in administering discipline, being firm and emphatic with the adolescent's need.
- * Parents should communicate with their adolescents regularly and freely, using punishment sparingly and listening to them patiently by noting verbal and non-verbal signals they use.
- * Parents should provide them with basic life needs i.e. food, clothing, house and shelter.
- * Parents should provide face to face i.e. one-on-one counselling from time to time in a warm and friendly environment.
- * Share their concerns and always feel responsible for their well being and safety.
- * Provide all forms of education for them viz formal, informal and non-formal.
- * Keep the line of communication open and listen to than more.

Other counselling strategies that could be employed by parents are:

- (a) Spend time together with their adolescents
 - (b) Have fun during leisure
 - (c) Establish and maintain good rapport
 - (d) Keep up with their interests
 - (e) Take a walk or drive together.
- Take more interest and commitment to their general growth and well being socially, emotionally, cognitively psychologically and spiritually.
- Assist them to meet their life needs and challenges, their basic needs are: (i) someone to talk to about their goals and aspirations (ii) good friend and companion (iii) sense of identify individuality.
- Train and equip them with social skills like interpersonal human relations, community services, citizenship activities, economic management, etc. Most importantly put in place certain peer control mechanism.

Omoegun (1995) posited that the combination of availability, appreciation, affection and acceptance are magical counselling strategies which parents of adolescents must adopt for successfully parenting adolescents to adulthood. She stated further that parents should discourage family arguments, stress, conflicts, general negative parenting behaviours such as yelling, slapping, swiftly and nagging at the adolescent. By doing these, parents would be able to discourage anxiety, bullying or quick temperance of the adolescents, not only that but also be able to boost their self esteem and self confidence.

Adegoke (2003) opined that parents should embark on positive parenting project by engaging their adolescents in transitional training programmes including reiiigious and moral training.

Parents must show always that they value them and their uniqueness by displaying unconditional love, involve them in family responsibilities i.e.

taking important decisions, family finances, family properties, but this should be done with impurity as note of personal responsibility should be always sounded to them.

Lastly, parents should serve as role models, the expression "like father, like son" is a clear indication of how the behaviour of the child mirrors the home training given by the parents. The home remains the first place for character building and emulation of vices. Parents that smoke or drink alcohol openly or even send their children to buy such items should not expect something better from such children. Parenting should be "do as I do" but not do as "I ask you to do"

Conclusion

A child's job is to grow up and become an independent adult and the role of the parent is to help them through this developmental processes. The period of adolescence takes a vital place in this developmental process as it is made up of special traits and problems. At this stage parents often think that they become isolated and less important in the process, this is not so, the truth is that, adolescents need continued parental care, love, support and warmth relationship more than ever during this high risk period.

Concerned parents should therefore understand and treat these sets of children with special attention by adopting the aforementioned counselling strategies putting in mind that any failure of the adolescents is the failure of such parents'. The implication of such failure may be unhealthy for the parents, the community and the child himself. Whatever shape or form it takes, the biological parents bear the good and the bad than any other group. Therefore, parents should employ methods of positive parenting to attend to their growing children. This will make them become successful parents to be cherished by every member of the community to which they belong.

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